

**PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF COMMUNICATION
CULTURE FORMATION**

Fatullaev Azizjon Nasullo o'g'li

**Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management of the
National Research University of Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and
Agricultural Mechanization Engineers**

Annotation: In the article, important considerations should be made about the pedagogical, psychological, intellectual, ethical and aesthetic conditions for the formation of communication culture among teachers.

Key words: pedagogical process, communication culture, reflection, position, educational relations, education, training, self-education, communication and development, creative technologies, didactics.

Pedagogical conflicts and shortcomings that occur when the teacher starts pedagogical communication and ways to prevent them. Philosophical, social, psychological and pedagogical essence of the term "dialogue". Dialogue is a Greek word, conversation, conversation, interpersonal conversation and exchange of ideas, a form of oral speech, a conversation between two or more people. It is a transaction-information process. In dealing directly with individuals, a teacher gets a wide variety of information about his students, about the team as a whole, about its internal processes, etc. The pedagogue, in turn, informs his pupils of targeted information in the course of treatment. Looking at what kind of information the pedagogue receives through communication tools, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of information about the student's personality. Treatment allows a person to be trained in a wide variety of conditions and forms. While dealing with students, the teacher is able to understand even the smallest parts. Although these are not very significant from the outside, they can be signs of the manifestations of

necessary internal processes occurring in a person, which are very important for understanding him, in which the personality of the pedagogue plays a big role. The interpretation of the same phenomenon by different people is explained by its dependence on a person's past experience, which has three aspects: life experience in general, pedagogical activity experience, and the experience of dealing with a specific team and students.

Finally, the pedagogue's daily dealings with students lead to the fact that he notices the deep meaning and real reason in students' behavior in various situations, for which he uses as an example the evidence he often records and the behavior of students. uses character methods. The teacher's interaction with the students is considered as a means of education management, and also fulfills the role of a unifier. The transaction takes place within the framework of mutual relations. A transaction that is a control tool occurs before the activity. Behavior as a means of management contributes to the activity of students, and finally, it follows the activity of behavior as a means of management.

It is considered good manners. What kind of outlook and knowledge each person has is known from his behavior. Communication is a means of communication between people. Language is the main tool of communication. That is why it is called a tool of communication. If a person's language is sweet and his behavior is civilized, he will gain prestige among the people in a short time. Eloquence. It never brings prestige to a person. That is why our thinkers who lived in the past taught us to treat language and words with respect. Our great-grandfather Alisher Navoi expressed valuable thoughts about the culture of behavior, politeness, the importance of language, and sweetness, which have not lost their importance even for today. "A sweet tongue is pleasant to the heart, and gentleness is useful. A sweet word is as sweet as honey for pure hearts," says Alisher Navoi. In addition to teaching children, the pedagogue attaches great importance to the development of their speech, and in this he uses various

pedagogical methods.

The word "pedagogue" is important in the development of children's speech: on the one hand, speech is an important factor in the development of a child's education and thinking. It follows that the speech of the pedagogue should be figurative, beautiful and exemplary, and attract the child's attention. The speech itself is a measure, an indicator that shows how worthy the pedagogue's expertise is.

Therefore, working on speech and improving speech culture is the main social duty and responsibility of every pedagogue. The influence of speech in education is extremely great. A teacher's speech is a powerful tool that influences students' behavior, behavior, and thinking. The teacher's speech reflects his feelings, aspirations, will and faith. With the help of speech, he creates feelings of joy, encouragement, love, loyalty, anger, hatred in students. Standing together with the people, living together is called association. The beauty and politeness of people's relations with each other is called "Etiquette of communication". One of the greatest, but most complex and difficult activities of a person is finding his place and living among people, that is, in society. The complexity of this activity is that in order to join the crowd, to live in harmony with them (separately), a person must have the appropriate treatment and attitude. Many people do not like a rude and rude person, whose behavior and attitude do not suit many people. People like and respect people who are cheerful, sweet-talking, brave, good-natured. One of the conditions for finding a decent place among people, living harmoniously and harmoniously is a person's humility. A humble person never brags about his achievements, his wealth, his knowledge, he is always modest and simple. But humility in a person must be sincere.

Words warm the human heart, words hurt the human heart. The folk saying "A needle heals a wound, a word does not heal" is not in vain. Because the power of words is immense. A person should be extremely careful with his words and

language. Some of our young people pay very little attention to words and language. First of all, it is necessary to teach young people the culture of behavior, not to be rude in front of adults, not to interrupt adults, not to talk back to older people. A culture of care is needed everywhere. At work, in transport, at home, that's why we need to know how to deal with whom. How educated and intelligent a person is is shown through behavior.

People convey and implement their entire inner world, purpose, behavior and relations to each other with the help of words. Because of this, life requires that communication relationships be extremely beautiful and gentle. Talkative, sweet-talking people have pleasant manners and good work. People like and respect such people. Conversation is also an art of its own. Perfect learning of this art is necessary for every person. At the same time, learning the native language is a sacred duty of every person. After knowing the language: it is necessary for a person to master the art of using it. Sweetness and beautiful speech are never sold anywhere. There is only one way to achieve this, and that is to practice sweet-talking without ceasing. This is mainly done by reading a lot of books. Behavior is the face of a person. Pedagogical activity of the teacher, first of all, is inextricably linked with the acquisition of personal meaning for him as an expert. This situation reflects the principle of logical hierarchy, because education determines the efficiency of a person depending on the indicator of development (both the teacher and the student) and the product of cooperation. In the same regard, the formation and development of pedagogical activity, the owners of these professions, cannot rule in isolation from the personality orientation. Therefore, researching the problem from the point of view of limitation between professional development and social development is an urgent task of pedagogy.

Pedagogical activity has an important social and educational value in society. After all, it is an activity that connects the chain of times and prepares generations for life economically, politically, spiritually, morally and aesthetically.

Therefore, it can be rightly said that pedagogical activity is the oldest activity and is a socio-pedagogical phenomenon. Even in the primitive period of the development of human society, in order to live, to save and continue the generation, in the process of fighting against the whims of nature and spontaneous forces, practical pedagogical activity was created and regulated. "This is a practical pedagogical activity," writes the Russian pedagogue I.F. Kozlov, - is the summation of the activities of various educational institutions, adults, ancestors, parents, teachers, schools in order to direct and manage the education of students according to the purpose" [1].

Pedagogical profession performed a very important task for the society, for its socio-economic development, because then it carried out the succession to prepare the future generation for life. In this case, pedagogy is not a profession, but educator - mudarris. Since education is a necessary means of social life, engaging in this profession brought the profession of education to the field. The old ancestor taught the future generation the life experiences he had accumulated. The activity was carried out directly in the labor process. According to the information of the history and theory of pedagogy, at the seeding stage of the primitive community system, the people of the society were divided into three groups: the first group consisted of newborn babies and children who could not work; the second group is made up of full-fledged masters of work and life, that is, those who take care of the members of the community with work, and the third group is made up of old people and old people who have lost the ability to do physical work. The work of preparing the young generation for life, teaching them life experiences, raising the young generation to be resilient, strong-willed and physically developed, and training them for training, is the responsibility of the third group of people, that is, the elderly and the elderly who have lost the ability to work physically, and they are the educators of the young. - those named after their teachers. In the slave society, in connection with the appearance of slaves and slaveholders, in the period

when human activity consisted of such types of work as mental work and physical work, priests were engaged in mental work. He worked for them as a teacher. Priests, nobles, zamindars, merchants, had private tutors because they were well-off. In addition to teaching children physical and mental work, these teachers performed tasks such as self-awareness, learning about the world around them, and preparing themselves for life.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Kozlov I.F. Pedagogicheskiy opyt A.S.Makarenko.-M.:1987, s-43
2. Gonobolin F.N.O‘qituvchi haqida qissa.-Toshkent, “O‘qituvchi”, 1965, 14-bet
3. Safarov, T. T. (2021). BUKHARA GUZARS AND THEIR ROLE IN THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE OF THE CITY. CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF HISTORY, 2(11), 13-17.
4. Safarov, T. T., & Nayimov, C. N. (2021). The Place of Markets and Caravansalities in Trade Between the Emirates of Bukhara and Russia. European Scholar Journal, 2(5), 169-171.
5. Ramazonov, J., & Xomidov, M. (2024). MILLIY QADRIYATLAR ASOSIDA SHAXS MA’NAVIY KAMOLOTI SHAKLLANISHINING IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций, 3(1), 200-202.
6. Ramazonov, J. (2022). ШАХСДА РЕФЛЕКСИЯ ДАРАЖАЛАРИНИНГ ЎСИБ БОРИШ ДИНАМИКАСИНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ ПСИХОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 10(10).
7. Ramazonov, J. (2021). Reflexive Mechanism-As The Main Form Of Controlling Students' Psychological Conditions. Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu. uz), 7(7).
8. Ramazonov, J. (2022). SELF-ADMINISTRATION AS A SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 9(9).

